

Inclusion complexation of hydroxybenzenes with natural and modified α - and β -cyclodextrins

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Abstract : Host-guest association between four hydroxybenzenes such as 1,2-dihydroxybenzene (2DHB), 1,3-dihydroxybenzene (3DHB), 1,4-dihydroxybenzene (4DHB) and 1,2,3-trihydroxybenzene (THB) with α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD were carried out using UV-Visible, steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence, FT-IR, ^1H NMR and semi-empirical methods (PM3). Stoichiometry ratios, binding constants and stability of the inclusion complexes were studied, showing that 1 : 1/host : guest complexes was formed. From the computational study, we found that (i) the stability of the four inclusion complexes are the same, (ii) the four HBs are fully encapsulated into the CDs, (iii) the negative Gibbs energy and enthalpy changes for the inclusion complexes indicated that the formation of these complexes is spontaneous and exothermic, (iv) hydrogen bonding interactions play a major role in the inclusion process and (v) the computational results indicate that the formation of all the inclusion complexes are enthalpy driven process.

Keywords : Dihydroxybenzenes, cyclodextrins, inclusion complex, supramolecular chemistry, semi-empirical calculation.

Introduction

Cyclodextrins (CD) are cyclic oligomers of α -D-glucose, crystalline, non-hygroscopic, and torus-like macro cycles, formed by the action of certain enzymes on starch and have been studied extensively as a host molecule in supramolecular chemistry¹. The glucose units are connected through glycosidic α -1,4 bonds². The three most commonly used CD is : α -CD (six glucose units), β -CD (seven glucose units) and γ -CD (eight glucose units). CD has a large intramolecular cavity; they have ability to include guest molecules altering their physical, chemical, biological and pharmacological properties through the formation of inclusion complexes. The size of the cavity of α -CD is more adequate to interact with a great number of molecules¹⁻⁴ and this CD was used in this study. The CD is often used to increase the aqueous solubility, stability and bioavailability of drugs^{5,6}. Besides, CD has numerous advantages as a host material : (1) they are biocompatible and are produced naturally in the enzymatic degradation of starch, (2) they are relatively cheap, and (3) are non-toxic, permitting applications in drugs, foods and cosmetics.

Drug solubility and stability are two very important

factors with respect to drug administration and drug delivery. In recent years, to overcome the drugs stability and solubility limitations, several approaches have been investigated. Cyclodextrins (CDs) have been extensively used as complexing agents to improve solubility and stability of a variety of poorly soluble and labile drugs. Cyclodextrins are cyclic organic compounds obtained by enzymatic transformation of starch. Among this class of "host" molecules, the β -CD is one of the most abundant natural oligomers and corresponds to the association of seven glucose units exhibiting a cavity with a hydrophobic character whereas the exterior is strongly hydrophilic. This peculiar structure allows guest molecules to be included into the cavity via non-covalent bonds to form inclusion complexes⁷. Natural CDs have limited water solubility that negatively influences water solubility and the stability of the formed complex. To overcome this problem alkyl moiety, such as hydroxyalkyl or methyl, on free hydroxyl groups of β -CD were introduced. The complexing ability of CD derivatives was significantly modified in respect to the parents. The potential use of natural cyclodextrins and their synthetic derivatives for improvement of the solubility, stability and/or

bioavailability by formation of inclusion complexes with drugs has been extensively studied^{8,9}.

Computer-aided molecular modeling methods have been recently proposed as powerful tools for obtaining information about the three-dimensional structures and the interaction emerging of the inclusion complexes¹⁰. In addition, molecular modeling study of host-guest interactions between CD and drug molecules should provide better insights into these interactions. In recent years, various molecular modeling studies have been performed to investigate CD inclusion complexes aiming at comprehending the mechanism of the complexation and correlating the experimental results with the mode of the interaction between host and guest inclusion using the PM3 or PM6 semi-empirical methods¹¹⁻¹⁶, AutoDock molecular docking¹⁷ and molecular dynamics simulations¹⁸.

In our previous work, we have reported the spectral characteristics of various drug and dye molecules in aqueous β -CD¹²⁻¹⁶. In this paper, the effect of α -CD and β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene (2DHB), 1,3-dihydroxybenzene (3DHB), 1,4-dihydroxybenzene (4DHB) and 1,2,3-trihydroxybenzene (THB) were investigated. The inclusion complexes of these molecules with α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD were investigated by UV-Visible, steady state fluorescence, time resolved fluorescence and molecular modeling methods. The aim of this investigation is to study the inclusion complex between the above mentioned molecules with CDs specifically to determine (i) optimum geometrical structure, (ii) the nature of intermolecular binding, (iii) the conformational changes of these molecules inside CD cavity, and (iv) the stability of the complex.

Experimental

Reagents and methods :

All the HBs and CDs were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used as such. Solutions in the pH range 2.0–12.0 were prepared by adding appropriate amount of phosphate buffer (NaOH and H₃PO₄). Triply distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. The solutions were prepared just before taking measurements. The concentration of the drug solutions were in the order of 4×10^{-4} to 4×10^{-5} M. The concentrations of CDs were varied from 1×10^{-3} to 10×10^{-3} M. The experiments were carried out at room temperature 303 K.

Instruments :

Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (model 1650) and fluorescence measurements were made by using a Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter (model RF-5301). The pH values in the range 2.5–12.0 were measured on an Elico pH meter (model LI-120). The fluorescence lifetime measurements were performed using a picoseconds laser and single photon counting setup from Jobin-Vyon IBH.

Molecular modeling :

The theoretical calculations were performed with Gaussian 03W package. The initial geometry of the HBs and the CDs were constructed with Spartan 08 and then optimized by PM3 (Parametric method 3). Both CDs were fully optimized by PM3 without any symmetry constraint¹⁹⁻²⁴. The glycosidic oxygen atoms of CD were placed onto the XY plane and their centre was defined as the centre of the coordination system. The primary hydroxyl groups were placed pointing toward the positive Z axis. The inclusion complexes were constructed from the PM3 optimized the CD and the guest molecules. The longer dimension of the guest molecule was initially placed onto the Z axis. The position of the guest was determined by the Z coordinate of one selected atom of the guest. The inclusion process was simulated by putting the guest in one end of CD and then letting it pass through the CD cavity. Since Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations are expensive (cost and takes long time) in treating such large molecular systems, we used single point energy calculations to the PM3 optimized geometries using semiempirical method as implemented in Gaussian 03W¹⁹⁻²³.

Results and discussion

Effect of cyclodextrins with HBs :

Table 1 show the absorption and fluorescence maxima of 2DHB, 3DHB, 4DHB and THB (4×10^{-5} M) in buffer solutions (pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7) containing various concentrations of α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD. Figs. 1 to 4 depict the absorption and fluorescence spectra of the above HBs molecules in all the CD solutions. With an increasing the concentration of the CDs, no significant absorption spectral shift was observed, whereas in β -CD, the absorption maximum is red shifted in all the

Table 1. Absorption, fluorescence, lifetime of 2DHB, 3DHB, 4DHB and THB in water and α -CD and β -CD environments

Compd.	Medium	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\langle \tau \rangle$	Binding constant (K^{-1})		ΔG (kcal mol^{-1})	
						abs	flu	abs	flu
2DHB	Water	275	3.31	330	0.09				
		218	3.98						
	α -CD	275	3.42	330	0.15	143	176	2.98	-3.10
		218	4.12						
	β -CD	276	3.80	340	0.21	247	248	3.31	-3.31
		210	4.16						
3DHB	Water	273	3.34	310	1.64				
		222	3.97						
	α -CD	273	3.43	310	6.06	189	349	3.13	-3.52
		221	4.07						
	β -CD	277	3.35	310	7.65	365	621	3.55	-3.87
		229	4.15						
4DHB	Water	289	3.42	330	0.16				
		223	3.78						
	α -CD	289	3.57	330	0.22	153	592	3.02	-3.84
		222	3.89						
	β -CD	295	4.10	330	0.32	191	192	3.16	-3.16
		223	3.95						
THB	Water	266	3.39	340	0.08				
		218	3.98						
	α -CD	266	3.51	340	0.06	163	276	3.06	-3.38
		216	4.13						
	β -CD	263	3.89	340	0.09	63	148	2.48	-3.02
		221	4.15						

HB molecules. The absorbance of the four guest molecules were increased with increasing α -CD concentrations. Interestingly, the spectral shapes of the HB molecules in all the CD solutions were similar to each other. The insert Figs. 1 to 4 depicts the changes in the absorbance and fluorescence intensities were observed as a function of the CDs concentration added²⁴⁻³¹.

Figs. 3 and 4 illustrate the influence of increasing concentration of CDs on the fluorescence spectrum of HBs at room temperature. Notably, adding CDs to the guest solution has significantly increased the fluorescence intensity of HBs. Such observation could be attributed mainly to the role of the apolar cavity of CDs in stabilizing the HBs molecules during the excitation-relaxation phenomenon. In particular, the apolar cavity provides protection for the HBs at the excited state against various deactivation processes, such as collisions with water molecules in the bulk solutions and internal conversion that

may reduce the fluorescence intensities of the HB molecules. These observations suggest that stable inclusion complexes between CDs and HBs were formed.

The presence of isosbestic point suggested the possibility of a single equilibrium involving 1 : 1 complexation between HBs and the CDs. The similar absorption and emission spectral shifts noticed in the CDs indicate that similar type of inclusion complexes was formed. In order to determine the stoichiometry of the inclusion complex, the absorbance and fluorescence dependence for all molecules on CDs were analyzed by using the Benesi-Hildebrand equation³². A plot of $1/\Delta A$ or $1/I - I_0$ versus $1/[\text{CDs}]$ gave a very good linear line as shown in Fig. 5. This analysis showed all molecules formed 1 : 1 inclusion complexes with CDs.

It is well known that the efficiency of the complexation process of CDs with various guest molecules depends mainly on their molecular sizes and polarities, which

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of DHBs in different α -CD concentrations (M) : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Fig. : absorbance vs $[\alpha\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of DHBs in different β -CD concentrations (M) : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Fig. : absorbance vs $[\beta\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of DHBs in different α -CD concentrations (M) : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Fig. : fluorescence intensity vs $[\alpha\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of DHBs in different β -CD concentrations (M) : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Fig. : fluorescence intensity vs $[\beta\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 5. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the 1 : 1 complexation of DHBs with α - and β -cyclodextrin : Plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[CDs]$. Plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[CDs]$.

in turn determine the driving forces that lead to the formation of inclusion complexes of CDs with various molecules³³. Therefore, it is essential to perform quantitative analysis that can provide some insights on the extent of the complexation process. Hence, the binding constant (K) is considered as the most important parameter in studying the inclusion complexation process of CDs, which in turn provides extensive details about the efficiency of the inclusion process. Thus, the enhancement in the fluorescence intensities of the guest molecules upon forming inclusion complexes with CDs was used for determining binding constant.

Effect of pH in aqueous and CDs medium :

To know the effect of CD on the prototropic equilibrium between neutral and monoanion, the pH dependent changes in the absorption and emission spectra of all molecules in aqueous and CDs medium were recorded. In aqueous and CD medium, the absorption and fluorescence spectra were studied in the $H_0/pH/H$ range of -1 to 11. The results are summarized as below : In all the CDs, with the decrease on pH from 7, the absorption spectrum of all molecules was unaffected upto pH \sim 1. When the

pH was increased from 5 to pH \sim 10, the absorption maximum was moved to longer wavelength. This is due to the formation of the monoanion obtained by deprotonation of the hydroxyl group. Further increase in basicity of the solution the maxima are red shifted. The red shifted spectrum is due to the formation of a dianion obtained by the deprotonation of the second hydroxyl group. However in CD medium, with an increase in pH from 4 to \sim 10, the absorption maximum is unusually blue shifted. This is due to the formation of the monoanion of all the HBs. Since the CD hydroxyl group deprotonated above $pK_a \sim$ 11, the dianion values of HBs were not determined in CDs medium.

The fluorescence characteristic of the all molecules is similar to its absorption characteristics. In both the CDs, when the acidity increased, the emission intensity of the fluorescent band decreased considerably as the consequence of monocation formation. With an increase in the pH from 5, the emission intensity of the fluorescent band was quenched at the same wavelength suggesting monoanion was formed. The formation of monoanion was completed in the pH range 10-11.

Unlike aqueous medium, in all the CDs, the anions were largely blue shifted. The tendencies of these blue shifts in λ_{abs} of the all HBs are attributed to the inclusion of the HB monoanions into the hydrophobic cavity of CD. This is because the interior CD cavity is less polar than the aqueous phase. In the less polar environment of CD, the dipole-dipole interactions between the environment in CD and the HB will be lowered.

Excited singlet state life times :

The formation of inclusion complex was also studied by the fluorescence decay curves obtained for all the four CDs. The fluorescence life times of the HB molecules in aqueous and CDs medium were determined from the decay curves and are given in Table 1. Tri exponential decay was noticed in 2DHB and THB in aqueous and the CDs solution whereas, biexponential decay were observed in 3DHB and 4DHB. From Table 1, the life times of the inclusion complexes were greater than the HBs molecules. This may be due to the vibration restriction of the HBs in the excited state. The increase in the lifetime with increase in the concentrations of CDs is due to the encapsulation of all molecules in the CD cavity. The above results indicated the tendency of complexation ability of CD, in other words β -CD has given the higher encapsulation.

Molecular modeling :

In order to gain more information about the inclusion complexes as described in the above experimental results, semiempirical quantum mechanical calculations of the complexes were performed at PM3 level. This study revealed that a preferred final relative orientation for all the complexes occurred in spite of the different initial configurations arbitrarily imposed. We also carried out PM3 calculation on the ground state geometry of guest molecules. The optimized structure, bond distances, bond angles and most out of the ordinary dihedral angles in these molecules before and after complexation considered by PM3 method are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The optimized structures of stable inclusion complexes are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. From the evaluation of data, the structures of the free guests were found completely altered after complexation. Considering the shape and dimensions of the α -CD and β -CD, these guests (HBs) could be completely entrapped in the CD cavities because

the lengths of all the HBs are smaller than that of the CDs cavity. From the PM3 calculations, the conformation obtained had both the hydroxyl group of the molecules oriented toward the secondary rim of the CD cavity and the phenyl ring is located in the primary rim of the CD cavity.

The complexation energy allowed us to evaluate the inclusion process and to find the most stable inclusion complex between the complexes studied. It was evaluated as

$$\Delta E_{\text{complexation}} = E_{\text{complex}} - (E_{\text{CD}} - E_{\text{HB}}) \quad (1)$$

where E_{complex} , E_{CD} and E_{HB} represent the total energy of the complex, the free optimized CDs and the free optimized HBs respectively. All complexation energies were negative which demonstrated that the inclusion processes of the guests in the CDs were thermodynamically favorable. The lowest values for complexation energy correspond to the most stable complex. The binding energy change for all the HB : β -CD inclusion complexes was more negative than the HB : α -CD complexes. This indicated that 4DHB : β -CD formed more stable inclusion complex.

The binding energy (ΔE) of the isolated and complex suggested that stability of the complexes was high compared to isolated molecules. From Tables 2 and 3, the dipole moment of 4DHB complex was larger than other complexes. The dipole moment of 2DHB is ~ 1.94 D, 3DHB is ~ 1.12 D, 4DHB is zero and THB is 2.19 D. This was lower than that of the inclusion complex, (2DHB : α -/ β -CD complex $\sim 11.63/11.78$ D, 3DHB : α -/ β -CD complex $\sim 11.53/11.12$ D, 4DHB : α -/ β -CD complex $\sim 10.77/12.29$ D and THB : α -/ β -CD complex $\sim 11.72/10.02$ D lower than the dipole moment for resident molecules. The above quantum mechanical computation values demonstrated a strong relationship with the complexation behavior.

The optimized structures in Figs. 6 and 7 shows two intermolecular hydrogen bonds present between hydrogen atom of hydroxyl group of the guests and oxygen atom of primary hydroxyl group of the CDs with a $d_{\text{H}\cdots\text{O}}$ distance less than 2.50 Å. This is justified by the importance of interaction energy between the guests and CDs necessary to ensure a better inclusion of the guests to the host. The above values were supported by the fact

Table 2. Binding energies and HOMO, LUMO energy of 2DHB, 3DHB, 4DHB and THB before inclusion complexation by PM3 method

Properties	2DHB	3DHB	4DHB	THB	α -CD	β -CD
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-8.92	-9.06	-7.85	-8.96	-10.38	-10.35
E_{LUMO} (eV)	0.24	0.27	0.14	0.26	1.26	1.23
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-9.16	-9.33	-8.89	-9.22	-11.64	-11.58
Dipole (D)	1.94	1.12	0	2.19	11.34	12.29
E^*	-65.16	-67.38	-66.18	-108.98	-1247.52	-1457.63
G^*	49.01	49.67	49.80	51.32	-571.21	-667.55
H^*	73.63	73.83	73.73	77.09	-676.73	-789.52
S^{**}	0.082	0.081	0.080	0.086	-0.353	-0.409
Zero point energy	68.54	68.93	68.76	71.54	634.47	740.56

Unit * = kcal mol⁻¹, ** = cal/mol Kelvin.**Table 3.** Binding energies and HOMO, LUMO energy of 2DHB, 3DHB, 4DHB and THB after inclusion complexation by PM3 method

Properties	2DHB-	2DHB-	3DHB-	3DHB-	4DHB-	4DHB-	THB-	THB-
	α -CD	β -CD						
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-8.54	-8.60	-9.12	-8.98	-8.75	-8.47	-8.75	-8.68
E_{LUMO} (eV)	0.51	0.51	0.24	0.36	0.21	0.46	0.35	0.55
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-9.05	-9.11	-9.36	-9.33	-8.96	-8.92	-9.10	-9.23
Dipole (D)	11.63	11.78	11.53	11.12	10.77	12.29	11.72	10.02
ΔD	-1.65	-2.45	-0.93	-2.29	-0.57	0	-1.81	-4.46
E^*	-1317.05	-1530.51	-1318.04	-1532.06	-1315.61	-1532.54	-1355.18	-1574.73
ΔE^*	-4.37	-7.72	-3.14	-7.05	-1.91	-8.73	1.32	-8.12
H^*	752.54	864.81	752.27	865.02	752.29	865.04	756.62	868.79
ΔH^*	-2.18	-1.66	-1.71	-1.67	-1.83	-1.79	-2.80	-2.18
G^*	637.35	732.73	638.86	732.45	638.48	731.74	643.82	734.02
ΔG^*	-17.13	-16.17	-17.98	-15.23	-17.47	-14.39	-21.29	-15.15
S^*	0.386	0.443	0.380	0.444	0.381	0.447	0.378	0.452
ΔS^*	0.049	0.048	0.054	0.046	0.052	0.042	0.061	0.043
Zero point energy	705.57	810.63	705.81	810.81	705.62	810.62	709.78	813.54

Unit * = kcal mol⁻¹, ** = cal/mol Kelvin.

that the flexibility of the host molecules may be one of the structural requirements for inclusion complexes formation.

Further the results in Tables 4 and 5 confirmed that hydrogen bonding interactions played a major role in the inclusion complexation process. The ' K ' values are a reasonable measure of hydrogen bonding and the change in hydrogen bonding of the guests is caused only by the hydrogen ion concentrations³⁴. Since the HB molecules polar substituents are located near the wider end of the CDs cavities and phenyl ring is located near the narrower range of the CDs cavities, the ' K ' values are proportional to the hydrogen bonding interactions. The energy involved

in such hydrogen bond interaction is responsible for the higher/lower binding constants compared to those of the substituted/unsubstituted molecules. The difference in slope in Fig. 5 for these inclusion complexes indicated that the interactions of hydrogen atoms of the guests with CDs were much stronger confirming the interactions were due to the hydrogen bonding.

Thermodynamics of inclusion process :

The energetic features, thermodynamic characteristics and electronic properties of these structures were summarized in Tables 2 and 3. HOMO-LUMO energy gap of the HBs was calculated using PM3 and are shown in Fig. 8, which reveals that the energy gap reflected the chemi-

Fig. 6. The inclusion complex structure of (a) 2DHB, (b) 3DHB, (c) 4DHB and (d) THB with α -CD.

Fig. 7. The inclusion complex structure of (a) 2DHB, (b) 3DHB, (c) 4DHB and (d) THB with β -CD.

cal activity of the molecules. LUMO as an electron acceptor represents the ability to obtain an electron and HOMO represents the ability to donate electron. Moreover, a lower HOMO-LUMO energy gap explained the eventual stability of the complex i.e. isolated molecule had lower stability than complex molecule.

Further the ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) gap is an important scale of stability³⁵ and chemicals with large ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) values tend to have higher stability. So we investigated the electronic structure of the complexes in with these considerations using PM3 method. The HOMO-LUMO value of 3DHB : β -CD complex is more negative than other inclusion complexes. This suggests 3DHB : β -CD inclusion complex is more stable than the other inclusion complexes. In fact, the increase of the ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) gap for the complexes is a new confirmation. However, the energy gap between HOMO and LUMO of each complex suggested that there will be no significant change in the electronic spectrum of the guest molecules driving molecular recognition and binding. Further, we noticed that the dipole moment values of the CDs and free HBs increased when the hydrophobic guest entered into the CD cavity and the complex was formed which was an indication of the increase of the polarity.

From the results, we noticed that, complexation reactions of these four guests with all the CDs are exothermic judged from the positive enthalpy changes which suggested that these inclusion processes are enthalpy driven in nature. The enthalpy changes for HBs/CD inclusion complexes were attributed to the more strong van der Waals interactions between the guests and CDs. Further, for all the complexes, the entropy and Gibbs free energy changes were negative which implied that the inclusion processes were spontaneous at room temperature. The differences between the experimental and theoretical values were due to solvent effect. The experiments were conducted in aqueous medium and the computational work was done at vacuum phase. We were unable to do the computational work at the aqueous medium due to system limitation.

Recently, some authors who encountered this discrepancy turned to experimental values to adjust their calculations. For example in the case of the complexes of both *cis* and *trans* isomers of Brooker's mercyanine inserted within β -CD cavity, the author's preliminary calculations of ΔG values predicted the complex would not form spontaneously and the magnitude and the sign of ΔS and ΔG values were very different from the experiment values¹²⁻¹⁴. They argued that since experimentally the entropy of complexation depends on both the insertion of the guest molecule and the concurrent displacement of water molecules

Table 4. Geometrical parameters of 2DHB and 3DHB before and after inclusion in α - and β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

	2DHB	2DHB : α -CD	2DHB : β -CD	3DHB	3DHB : α -CD	3DHB : β -CD
Bond length (Å)						
H1-H4	5.64	5.67	5.68	H1-H4	5.65	5.66
O1-H4	5.25	5.25	5.25	O1-H4	5.24	5.24
H6-H2	4.61	5.28	5.28	H5-H3	4.54	4.55
O1-O2	2.81	2.80	2.81	O1-O2	4.77	4.78
Bond angle (°)						
O1-C1-C2	117	124	124	O1-C1-C2	122	122
O1-C1-C6	122	116	115	O1-C1-C6	116	115
O2-C2-C3	115	123	123	O2-C3-C2	115	115
Dihedral angle (°)						
O1-C1-C2-O2	0	-0.35	-0.21	O1-C1-C2-C3	180	179
O2-C1-C6-C5	180	-178	-176	O2-C3-C4-C5	180	-179
O1-C1-C6-C5	180	179	176	O1-C1-C6-C5	180	-179

Table 5. Geometrical parameters of 4DHB and THB before and after inclusion in α - and β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

	4DHB	4DHB : α -CD	4DHB : β -CD	THB	THB : α -CD	THB : β -CD
Bond length (Å)						
H1-H4	6.39	6.40	6.39	H1-H4	5.68	5.65
O1-H4	5.50	5.51	5.50	O1-H4	5.25	5.26
H6-H2	4.33	4.34	4.34	H6-H2	5.29	4.57
				O1-O3	4.82	4.81
Bond angle (°)						
O1-C1-C2	122	116	112	O1-C1-C2	116	117
C1-C2-C3	119	119	119	C4-C5-C6	120	121
Dihedral angle (°)						
O1-C1-C2-C3	180	-178	179	O1-C1-C2-O2	0	2.62
C1-C2-C3-C4	0	-0.15	-0.30	O3-C3-C4-C5	180	-179

that are trapped within the β -CD cavity, the water molecule should be included in the calculations and then they found thermodynamic values closer to the experimental results and the sign matched the reported values in all cases. Further Xing *et al.*³⁶ proposed a model to calculate ΔS of the inclusion complex in aqueous solution with the assumption that the effect of water molecules on the entropy changes of the 2-hydroxy-5-methoxyacetophenone : β -CD system is mainly determined by the water molecules in the β -CD cavity and the effect of the H₂O molecules out of the cavity is less important and thus can be negligible.

In Tables 4 and 5, we report the selected bond distances, bond angles and the most interesting angles between the hydroxyl group and phenyl ring of these mol-

ecules before and after complexation as calculated by PM3 method for the most stable inclusion complex. From comparison of free guest and the complex, it is clear that the geometrical structure of the HBs after complexation is completely altered. This alteration was achieved through the variation of the dihedral angles between the phenyl ring and the OH group of these guests which was subject to a distortion to adopt a specific conformation leading to the formation of a most stable complex. The non bonded interaction between the phenyl ring and CD might be responsible for the difference in structure stability of the complex. Experimental thermodynamical values will be helpful for numerical investigations in order to draw a conclusion about the effect of the solvent on the binding of complexation.

Fig. 8. HOMO-LUMO energy structure of (a) 2DHB, (b) 3DHB, (c) 4DHB and (d) THB.

As can be noticed from Tables 2 and 3, the enthalpy and entropy changes have negative values, which suggests that the inclusion reaction is exothermic and more ordered-system is obtained after complexation. However, the high ΔH value in comparison to ΔS values indicates that the inclusion process is predominantly driven through enthalpy changes, which in turn can compensate for the unfavorable entropy changes. The observed small negative ΔS is a confirmation of restriction of freedom of the molecule and formation of more compact structures. Further, negative ΔG were obtained for all the HB molecules that were investigated which implies that the inclusion complexation reaction proceed spontaneously. Binding of all molecules with CDs is enthalpy-entropy favourable showing negative ΔH and ΔS values.

Solid inclusion complex studies :

Further to confirm the HB : CD inclusion complex interactions, we also prepared the solid inclusion complexes and characterized them by FTIR and ^1H NMR methods.

FTIR spectral studies :

(i) **2DHB** : The aromatic OH stretching frequency at 3461 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 3470 cm^{-1} respectively. The phenyl ring and C=C stretching frequency at 3326 cm^{-1} and 1620 cm^{-1} were moved in the inclusion complex to 3335 cm^{-1} and 1625 cm^{-1} respectively. The C-OH stretching frequency at 1188 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 1192 cm^{-1} .

(ii) **3DHB** : The aromatic OH stretching frequency at 3240 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 3254 cm^{-1} respectively. The phenyl ring and C=C stretching frequency at 3229 cm^{-1} and 1609 cm^{-1} were moved in the inclusion complex to 3235 cm^{-1} and 1615 cm^{-1} respectively. The C-OH stretching frequency at 1168 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 1176 cm^{-1} .

(iii) **4DHB** : The aromatic OH stretching frequency at 3262 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 3268 cm^{-1} respectively. The phenyl ring and C=C stretching frequency at 3031 cm^{-1} and 1628 cm^{-1} were moved in the inclusion complex to 3040 cm^{-1} and 1635 cm^{-1} respectively. The C-OH stretching frequency at 1164 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 1170 cm^{-1} .

(iv) **THB** : The aromatic OH stretching frequency at 3636 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 3639 cm^{-1} respectively. The phenyl ring and C=C stretching frequency at 3335 cm^{-1} and 1623 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 3340 cm^{-1} and 1635 cm^{-1} respectively. The C-OH stretching frequency at 1169 cm^{-1} was moved in the inclusion complex to 1180 cm^{-1} . The above results confirmed that all the molecules were encapsulated in the CDs cavity.

^1H NMR spectral studies :

NMR studies allowed us to distinguish between inclusion and other possible external interaction processes. In fact, NMR is the most powerful technique used to determine the inclusion of a guest molecule into the hydrophobic CDs cavities, in solution. It is well known that the chemical shifts of the hydrogen atoms located in the interior of the CDs cavities (H-3 and H-5) become shielded and usually show significant upfield shift in the presence of a guest molecule, whereas the hydrogen atoms on the outer surface (H-1, H-2 and H-4) are not affected or experience only a marginal shift upon complexation. ^1H NMR spectra of the 2DHB, 3DHB, 4DHB and THB inclusion

complexes were performed at 25 °C in D₂O and compared with those of pure compounds. The variation of the chemical shifts of the HBs and the inclusion complexes (in bracket) were given below :

(i) 2DHB and its inclusion complexes : OH : 9.26 (9.31), 3H and 6H : 6.92 (6.97), 4H and 5H : 6.84 (6.89); (ii) 3DHB and its inclusion complexes : OH : 9.15 (9.19), 2H : 6.22 (6.24), 4H and 6H : 6.21 (6.23) and 5H : 6.92 (6.95); (iii) 4DHB and its inclusion complexes : OH : 8.59 (8.63) and 2,3,5 and 6H : 6.58 (6.62); (iv) THB and its inclusion complexes : 4H and 6H : 6.60 (6.65) and 5H : 6.75 (6.78).

¹H NMR spectra are one of the most direct evidences for the formation of the inclusion complex¹²⁻¹⁴. The changes of chemical shifts ($\Delta\delta$) in the complex were rather small, since there were no direct chemical bonds formed between CD and the HB molecules of the complex. The interactions between host and guest molecules are noncovalent bonds such as van der Waals forces, hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonds¹²⁻¹⁴. H-3 and H-5 protons were located inside the cavity, H-3 closer to the wider rim and H-5 on the opposite. Due to the free rotation of the primary hydroxyl on the smaller rim leading to the steric effect, the most likely mode of complexation was insertion of the less polar moiety of the guest into the CDs cavities from the wider rim resulting in obvious upfield shifts in the signals for H-3 than H-5. The upfield shift is due to the ring current effect of aromatic part of the guest. The difference in $\Delta\delta$ values of the HBs and the inclusion complex indicated that the molecules completely enter into the CD cavity. When the complex was formed, the CD H-3 proton located above the ring current of the phenyl ring made it to be shielded resulted in upfield shift, while H-5 proton presented downfield shift owing to the deshielding zone of the ring current. On the contrary, signals for the guest protons will probably show downfield shift changes upon complexation with CD.

As can be seen from the values, chemical shifts data for the inclusion complexes were slightly different from the free HB compounds. In particular, the resonance of the protons of all the HBs located within or near the cavity showed remarkable downfield shift (0.04 ppm) in the inclusion complexes. In all the above molecules, the aromatic ring hydrogen and OH group were shifted

downfield in the complex, which suggested that the aromatic ring was shielded largely in the complex and it must penetrate deeply into the cavity. Further, as can be seen from the above values, the resonance of all the molecules protons within the CDs cavities was shifted downfield when the inclusion complex was formed, which means that all the molecules preferred fixed orientation within the CD cavity.

Conclusion

The inclusion complexes of α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CDs with four HBs were investigated in aqueous solutions by UV-Vis, steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence, FTIR, ¹H NMR and molecular modeling techniques. The resultant inclusion complexes exhibit relatively high binding constants and were more hydrophobic than the free HBs. The formation of complexes is accompanied by negative enthalpy changes. The negative enthalpies agree with the fact that the van der Waals attractive CD-guest interactions are mainly responsible for the complexation.

From the computational study, we find that (i) the stability of the four inclusion complexes are the same, (ii) the four HBs are fully encapsulated into the CDs, (iii) the negative Gibbs energy and enthalpy changes for the inclusion complexes indicated that the formation of these complexes is spontaneous and exothermic, (iv) hydrogen bonding interactions play a major role in the inclusion process, (v) the dipole moment values for HBs increase when they enter into the cavities which is an indication of the increase of the polarity and the formation of complex and (vi) the computational results indicate that the formation of all the inclusion complexes are enthalpy driven process.

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